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Improving Home-Based Care Robots' Capabilities Using Natural Language

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Abstract

In the EU, the old-age dependency ratio is expected to rise to 51.2% by 2070. Personal Assistant Robots (PARs) can assist individuals and extend their independent living. This work aims to enhance communication and interaction capabilities between the robot and human within the home environment, thereby supporting older adults to better ageing in place.

Introduction

In the EU, the old-age dependency ratio $\frac{\geq 65}{15 \text{ to } 64}$ is projected to grow from 29.6% in 2016 to 51.2% in 2070 [1]. In ageing societies, the demand for long-term care will increase alongside shortages in labor to meet this demand [2]. Recent studies indicate evidence that robotic interventions could support “ageing in place” [3]. PARs can assist individuals and extend their independent living. Natural language interaction with robots is challenging, especially when translating high-level abstract instructions to the robot’s capabilities. Previous approaches vary from a set of predetermined instructions to explicit instructions such as Vision-and-Language Navigation (VLN) [4]. Recently, others have used a set of skills that the robot can

perform and use Large Language Models (LLMs) to select from these skills [5]. LLMs can encode extensive semantic knowledge about the world. A significant weakness of LLMs is their lack of real-world experience, which makes it difficult to leverage them for decision-making within a given robot's capabilities. LLMs without knowing the environment and the robot's capabilities can produce irrelevant outcomes. The aim of this research is to improve the robot's ability to understand and execute user verbal commands, utilizing extracted information from the environment and the robot's capabilities i.e., what the robot can/can't do and what the robot can/can't sense. To achieve the aim, we utilized pre-trained LLMs to analyze the end-user instructions and convert them into structured low-level commands that the robot can understand and execute and evaluated the ability of the robot to adapt to the changes in the environment to perform the user instructions. Evaluation is performed via NVIDIA Isaac Sim. Outcomes advance understanding of the role of LLMs in facilitating the capabilities of robots to effectively navigate and interact with environments to support the activities of daily living of older adults.

Personal Assistant Robot

A review was conducted to understand the needs and perspectives of older adults living independently and the availability of robots to support these individuals. Outcomes from the review helped determine the gap between users' needs and what can be achieved (in terms of independent living), why some solutions are adopted while others are not, and which areas (needs and robotic support) are in need of improvement. Further to the above the viewpoints and requirements of other stakeholders (clinicians, formal and informal caregivers) were considered. Table I presents outcomes from the review on robots available to support various users' needs. It shows that although there are some specialized robots for specific tasks, there is a significant gap in multi-functional assistive robots that can provide broad care for users with diverse needs. This shows the need for more research and development on robotics to support ageing in place. It indicates that for those needing assistance in multiple areas, a combination of several robots would be required or developing robots that can perform multi-functionalities.

After discussions with an expert in the field of robotics for old adults' assistance, we decided to focus on the need for an old adult named Cara. Cara likes gardening, but she cannot carry on the gardening tools herself. She wants the robot to carry the tools for her. Additionally, she wants the robot to remind her to take her medication and to fetch them.

Table I. Users' Needs vs. Available Robotics Systems

Users' Needs	ASTRO	Jaco	Care-O-bot4	ReWalk	PARO	AIBO	AmazonAstro	Bomy
Dressing								
Personal Hygiene								
Feeding		X						
Toileting								
Transferring/ Walking	X			X				
Transportation/ Shopping								
Managing Medications			X					X
Housework								
Social					X	X	X	X
Indoor Object Transferring			X				X	

Embodied AI with LLMs

To enable robots to navigate and interact with the surrounding environment, they need to have a representation that captures the semantic and geometric aspects of the scene at multiple levels of abstraction (objects, rooms, etc). Semantic representation provides a high level of abstraction for the robot to understand and execute human instructions, while geometric representation enables robots to navigate safely and manipulate objects [6]. To enable robots to plan execution for human instructions of high-level abstraction they need to convert the high-level instruction to an ordered list of primitive tasks that the robots can perform. LLMs can provide high-level knowledge about how to perform and covert complex and temporally extended instructions into a plan (containing an ordered list of primitive tasks) for execution, that the robots can perform. However, this requires understanding what is in the environment and the robot's capabilities to get relevant responses. Conditioning LLMs with visual scenes can provide affordable and reasonable responses in the corresponding environment. This could speed up the adoption of robots that can easily interact with humans and the environment. Additionally, it could provide reasoning ability to the robot to inform the users about failure to perform the task and the possible reason. Figure 1 shows the proposed architecture for using LLMs to control the robot. In future work, we will test the proposed architecture using robots with different embodiments such as a robot with a manipulator and a robot without, and report how the plan changes based on the robot embodiments and the environments.

Figure 1. The Proposed Framework for Using LLMs to Control the Robot: The Prompt Construction System obtains its inputs from scene description, robot description, task description, and abstract user instruction. Then the constructed prompt is fed to the LLM to output a plan as a set of sub-tasks that the robot can perform based on its capabilities. When the sub-task requires navigation Nav2 can perform the navigation. While, when the sub-task requires manipulation MoveIt2 will perform it.

Conclusion

This work aims to enhance communication and interaction capabilities between the robot and human within the home environment, thereby supporting older adults to better ageing in place. This work is to parse abstract language instructions provided by the end-user and convert them into navigation commands within the constraints of the robot’s capabilities by utilizing LLMs to provide a plan constrained by the robot’s capabilities. Robots hold promise in enhancing the quality of life for older adults and caregivers by assisting with ADL, IADL, and medical needs.

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